

Four methods of insecticide application for control of rice stem borers

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Four methods of applying insecticides recommended for control of rice stem borers were compared. There were seven treatments and four replications in a randomized complete block design. Plots measuring 2.5 × 5.5 m were planted to variety RD1. Insecticides carbofuran 3% G, triazophos 5% G, FMC 35001 40% EC, and monocrotophos 56% WSC were broadcast, used as root soaking treatment, and applied as, seedbed and foliar spray.

Broadcast carbofuran and triazophos at 1 kg a.i./ha and foliar sprays of FMC 35001 and monocrotophos were highly effective (see table). Yields were

Comparison of 4 methods of insecticide application for control of rice stem borers at the Khonkaen Rice Experiment Station, Thailand, 1978.^a

Treatment	Insecticide	Deadhearts (%) ^b	Yield (t/ha)
Broadcast ^c	Triazophos 5% G	0.67 a	1.5 bc
Broadcast ^c	Carbofuran 3% G	0.87 a	3.0 a
Foliar spray ^d	FMC 35001 40% EC	3.56 a	2.6 ab
Foliar spray ^d	Monocrotophos 56% WSC	4.53 ab	2.2 abc
Root soak ^e	Carbofuran 3% G	10.83 bc	1.5 bc
Foliar spray ^f	Monocrotophos 56% WSC	11.29 bc	1.8 bc
Root soak ^g	Carbofuran 3% G	12.03 c	1.4 bc
Seedbed ^h	Carbofuran 3% G	13.18 c	1.7 bc
Control	—	13.32 c	1.1 c
Seedbed ⁱ	Carbofuran 3% G	15.21 c	1.0 c

^aIn a column any 2 means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bCounted at 40 days after transplanting (DT). Percentage of deadhearts from other counts was too small to estimate.

^cApplied at 1 kg a.i./ha every 20, 40, and 60 DT.

^dSprayed at 1 kg a.i./ha every 20, 40, and 60 DT.

^eApplied at 10,000 ppm 2 days before transplanting (DBT).

^fSprayed twice at 1 kg a.i./ha when the infestation was more than 5%.

^gApplied at 5000 ppm 2 DBT.

^hApplied at 2 kg a.i./ha 20 days after seeding (DS).

ⁱApplied at 4 kg a.i./ha 20 DS.

lower where triazophos was broadcast. Foliar sprays of FMC 35001 and monocrotophos were more economical

than broadcast carbofuran. Root soaking and seedbed applications were not significantly different from the check. ■

Control of the rice bug by ultra-low-volume (ULV) spraying

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A water-based ULV spray of either gamma BHC or dichlorvos, applied once at flowering with a hand-held battery operated spinning disk sprayer, effectively reduced populations of the rice bug *Leptocorisa* sp. through the heading stage (see table). This reduction was not reflected in a significant gain in grain weight, number of grains per panicle, or a reduction in unfilled grains. But the significant reduction in the percentage of bug-damaged grains increased the quality of milled rice from grade two to one (as specified by the National Grains Authority of the Philippines).

By drifting fine, relatively uniform-sized droplets onto the crop, ULV spraying covers the panicles and foliage with a droplet density equivalent to the thorough wetting obtained with a knapsack sprayer. The volume rate of 8 liters is considerably less than the recommended 1,000 liters/ha.

Ultra-low-volume spraying of 2 insecticides against the rice bug *Leptocorisa* sp. on irrigated lowland rice; (variety, C4-63)^a, Batangas province, Philippines, 1978 wet season.

Treatment	Bugs ^b (no./m ²)			Damaged filled grains (%)
	2 DS	5 DS	10 DS	
Dichlorvos	1.1 a	0.5 a	0.0 a	0.6 a
Gamma BHC	1.3 a	0.5 a	0.3 ab	0.6 a
Control	3.4 b	2.2 b	0.9 b	2.3 b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bSprayed at flowering at 500 g ai/ha at a volume rate of 8 liters with an ULVA 8 sprayer.

DS = days after spraying.

With the savings in labor and chemicals, ULV spraying may be a viable alternative to the knapsack sprayer, particularly for small-scale farmers who underdose by

using volume rates that are too low.

IRRI is exploring the practicality of using ULV against the rice whorl maggot, stem borer, and brown planthopper. ■

Ovicidal activity of foliar sprayed insecticides on brown planthopper eggs

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Insecticides that can control the brown planthopper (BPH) have a short residual activity. Thus control is poor on nymphs that hatch a few days after insecticidal application. Timing of application would be less critical if the insecticide could kill eggs in addition to nymphs and adults.

To determine the ovicidal activity of several insecticides, BPH adults were allowed to oviposit for 24 hours on 25- to 30-day-old Taichung Native 1, a susceptible rice variety. One day after oviposition the plants were sprayed with the test insecticides at 0.75 kg a.i./ha. In a second experiment, BPH adults were allowed to oviposit for 48 hours. One day after oviposition the plants were sprayed with candidate compounds at 0.25 or 0.75 kg a.i./ha. Nymphs were removed and counted daily. At 14 days after oviposition, plants were dissected

and unhatched eggs counted.

Carbofuran, azinphos ethyl, and fenitrothion had ovicidal activity (see table). There was no hatch when carbofuran was applied at 0.75 kg a.i./ha, but the hatch was high (see table) with carbofuran at 0.25 kg a.i./ha. Fenitrothion slightly reduced egg hatch at the high rate in experiment 1, but had no ovicidal activity at the lower rate in experiment 2. ■

Ovicidal activity of certain insecticides on brown planthopper eggs. IRRI, 1979.

Insecticide and formulation	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Eggs hatched ^a (%)	Insecticide and formulation	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Eggs hatched ^a (%)
<i>Experiment 1</i>			<i>Experiment 2</i>		
Perthane 45 EC	0.75	97 c	Carbofuran 12 F	0.25	98 b
Methomyl 90 WP	0.75	97 c	Permethrin 10 EC	0.25	95 b
Fenitrothion +			Miral 50 EC	0.75	93 b
BPMC 75 EC	0.75	89 c	Fenitrothion 30 EC	0.25	85 ab
Fenitrothion 30 EC	0.75	78 b	Pirimiphos		
Azinphos ethyl 40 EC	0.75	7 a	ethyl 25 EC	0.75	84 ab
Carbofuran 12 F	0.75	0 a	Propoxur 20 EC	0.75	58 a
Check		100 c	Check		95 b

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. Av. 4 replications, each with 2 gravid females.

Recent records of natural enemies of the brown planthopper in India

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Studies in and around Mandya (Karnataka) and other areas during 1977-78 revealed the presence of the following natural enemies of the rice brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål (Homoptera, Delphacidae):

Nymphal and adult parasites

- Hymenoptera : Dryinidae - *Dryinus* sp.?
- " : " - *Haplogonotopus?* *orientalis* Roh.
- Strepsiptera : Elenchidae - *Elenchus* sp.
- " : Halictophagidae- *Halictophagus* sp.

Predators

- Coleoptera : Carabidae - *Elaphrus charis* (Andr.)
- " : Coccinellidae - *Coccinella repanda* Thunb.
- " : " - *Menochilus sexrnaculatus* (F.)
- Hemiptera : Anthocoridae - *Orius* sp.
- " : Nabidae - *Tropiconabis capsiformis* (Ger.)?
- " : Reduviidae - *Polytoxus* sp.

Nymphs and adults of *N. lugens* collected from the field at V. C. Farm, Mandya, were reared and dissected in the laboratory to estimate parasitism (see table).

Of the two strepsipterans, *Elenchus* sp. was the most numerous. One parasite per host was common, but occasionally two and rarely three individuals of some

Parasitism of *Nilaparvata lugens*, Mandya, India, April 1978.

Brown planthopper	Brown planthoppers examined (no.)	Parasitism ^a (%)		
		Dryinids	Strepsipterans	Total
Brachypterous female	88	10.2	21.6	31.8
" male	25	4.0	8.0	12.0
Macropterous female	31	3.2	19.4	22.6
" male	23	8.7	8.7	17.4
Av parasitism		7.8	17.4	25.2

^a*Echthrodelpfax fairchildii* Fallen (Dryinidae), earlier reported as a parasite of *N. lugens*, also contributed to the parasitism.

species were encountered in the same host. The triungulinids of *Elenchus* emerged in quick succession from the dorsolateral region of the host's posterior segment and crawled actively on the plant surface. About 1,500 triungulinids emerged from a brachypterous female host in about a minute. Another 1,000

larvae were recovered from the same host when it was dissected. The emergence of the parasite did not result in the immediate death of the host.

The predators listed fed on brown planthopper nymphs and adults and were found to also feed on several other insect pests. Their population was low. ■

Moth population fluctuation — a tool for forecasting stem borer outbreaks

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Pest forecasting plays an important role in the control of impending pest outbreaks in crops. When meteorological conditions favor the development of a potent pest, scientists can forecast the outbreak and warn the farmers to use precautionary plant-protection measures.

To develop a forecasting index scientists studied the fluctuations in stem borer moth populations in Faisalabad in 1972-73. Light traps were installed at different rice-growing locations from March until November. Moths were identified and the numbers of each species were averaged as weekly totals (see table).

The data show peaks in the moth populations of *Tryporyza innotata* and *T. incertulas*, and times when moth populations became alarming.

The first generation of white and yellow borers appeared on wing when the weather was warm. Adult formation was fastest in April, and slowed to a minimum by July — probably because of hot unfavorable temperatures and the lack of host crops in the preceding months. The moth populations of white and yellow borers were alarming from the last 2 weeks of August through September because of meteorological conditions. After tile monsoon rains, the temperature favors earlier moth emergence. If temperature remains mild because of a later or prolonged monsoon, the number of moths remains critical until the first 2 weeks of October. That is especially true for *T. incertulas*, which